

FOREIGN INVESTMENTS IN UZBEKISTAN AND CHANGES IN ECONOMIC LIFE IN 1992-2010 (IN THE CASE OF BUKHARA REGION)

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Annotation: this article reflects and analyzes the changes in foreign investment and economic life in Uzbekistan in 1992-2010 (on the example of Bukhara region).

Keywords: economic life, Foreign, foreign investors, economic potential, Bukhara, foreign countries.

Since the early years of independence, in 1991-1992 structural changes, diversification and modernization of economic sectors and branches continued consistently in Bukhara region as well as in other regions of the Republic. In the region, an active investment policy aimed at deepening the processes of technical and technological renewal of production, as well as the development of transport engineering, communication and social infrastructures has begun.

In terms of attracting investments, in 1992-1994, a number of foreign countries, far and near, started to establish relations with Bukhara region.

As it is known, the main principles of the Republic's economic prospects, the tasks in this regard were implemented step by step. By 1994-1995, a legal-normative framework was created, which allowed to accelerate the pace of transformation of state-owned enterprises into open joint-stock companies. Based on the approaches, goals, and priorities defined in the state privatization program, privatization was carried out by sectors and regions.

By 1995, more than 900 state-owned enterprises were privatized in the city of Bukhara alone, even in the trade and household service sectors, most of the production, construction and transport enterprises were privatized.

In 1995, the contribution of the state sector in the field of production and household services was 22.6% of the total volume. The contribution of joint-stock companies and privatized collective enterprises increased to 61.8% of the total volume. The contribution of individual enterprises was 14.7 percent of the total, and the contribution of joint enterprises was about 1 percent.

In 1995, the chartered fund of 82 cooperative societies operating in Bukhara was 267.2 million soums. Of this, 94.2 million soums or 35.2 percent is the State contribution, 80.3 million soums or 30.2 percent is the contribution of labor unions, 92.7 million soums or 34.6 percent is the contribution of investors released for free sale.

In particular, in 1995, a contract was signed with the German company "Siemens", and in 1996, it brought 10 water containers to Bukhara region. By installing the purchased containers, the consumption of water was low, but the motor time and electrical energy used by the water pumps were saved.

By 1995, the foreign trade turnover of Bukhara region with foreign countries reached the value of 631 million US dollars, including foreign trade turnover with the CIS countries was 56.5 million US dollars, and with foreign countries it reached 6.6 million US dollars. By 1996 alone, the volume of exports in foreign relations amounted to 41.6 million US dollars. 37.8 million dollars of this figure was contributed by the USA, and 3.8 million dollars by other foreign countries. Import volume reached 21.5 US dollars. 18.7 million US dollars of the above-mentioned value of imports fell to the CIS countries. Other foreign countries accounted for the remaining 2.8 million US dollars.

In 1995, imports amounted to 2.8 million US dollars, and economic relations were established with the following countries. Austria, Great Britain, Germany, Italy, USA, Turkey, Japan, France have invested.

15 years later, the following situation could be seen in the 2010 accounts. The turnover in the region was equal to 659.7 million US dollars, 266.2 million

US dollars of which were contributed by CIS countries, and 393.5 million US dollars were contributed by other foreign countries. It can be seen that, compared to 1995, foreign trade has increased 10 times by 2010. This growth indicator indicates that in 2010, there were ample opportunities for entrepreneurs.

By 2010, the total export volume was: 336.9 million US dollars. Of this, trade with the CIS countries was 42.9 million US dollars, and with other foreign countries 294 million US dollars.

In 1995-2010, cotton fiber, food products and similar light industrial products were exported from Bukhara to foreign countries. Compared to 1995, cotton fiber was 18.2 million US dollars in 2010 (193.0 in 2010), food products were 1.2 million US dollars (11.9 in 2010), other products were 22.2 million US dollars (52.8 in 2010).

In 1995, food products imported to Uzbekistan from foreign countries amounted to 7.7 million US dollars (4.5 in 2010), chemical products and plastic 0.1 (13.9 in 2010), energy sources 0.1 (216.4 in 2010), machinery and equipment amounted to 4.2 (53.4 in 2010) million US dollars.

Foreign-invested enterprises in the Bukhara region had a high share in the above-mentioned foreign trade turnover. In 1995, there were 25 foreign invested enterprises operating in Bukhara region. 12 of them were industrial, 1 was transport and communication, 1 was construction, 11 were various types of service enterprises. In 1995, the volume of production, works, and services in these enterprises was 41.2 million dollars. Exports amounted to 1,362,900 US dollars, while imports amounted to 15,200 US dollars. In 1995, 650 people were employed in joint ventures. The cost of paying these people's fees amounted to 4.7 million soums.

Since 1995, Bukhara region has continuously increased the number of joint ventures with foreign countries on the basis of foreign investment (investment) based on mutual cooperation, exchange of goods and equal partnership. These

enterprises provide industry, construction and various other similar services. In 1995, the number of these enterprises was 25, and fifteen years later, in 2010, the number of enterprises built on the basis of foreign investment reached 60. 49 of these enterprises were established at the expense of foreign investments in industry, 1 in transport and communications, 1 in construction, and 9 in other service sectors. The volume of production, works, and services in 2010 was 178,490.9 million soums. In this year, the export amounted to 46135.2 thousand US dollars. And the import was equal to 40007.9 thousand US dollars. The costs of payment of wages amounted to 9350.3 million soums.

Between 1995 and 2010, the Bukhara region was constantly establishing foreign relations with the above-mentioned countries. The representatives of these countries always visited the Bukhara region for the purpose of cooperation and held negotiations on improving and expanding their mutual relations.

It is known that increasing the effectiveness of the export potential of the regions largely depends on the supply and demand in the world raw materials market. The analysis of demands and needs observed in the world market shows that the development of the export potential in the region of Bukhara region in the near future depends on the sharp increase in the volume of exports of machinery, industrial products and processed household products. Because in the last 10 years, the world market has seen stable prices and constant demands for these and similar products.

The fuel and energy complex opens the way to great prospects in expanding the export capacity of the Bukhara region. Currently, the export potential of Bukhara, Kashkadarya and Fergana regions has increased significantly due to effective use of existing oil and gas reserves. In particular, in 1996-1998, the first block of an oil refinery was launched in Bukhara region in cooperation with foreign investors (France and Turkey - F.T.). The capacity of this plant is designed to produce 2 million tons of gas condensate and 5 million

tons of oil products per year. In 2009-2010, oil and gas condensate, which is the main raw material for carbohydrate production, increased its export volume due to product processing.

In fact, by 2010, the production of oil and gas condensate increased, due to which the export of goods also increased. Even after 5 years, this indicator has been constantly increasing. That is why foreign countries have been increasing their investments in Bukhara region year by year. By the beginning of 2015, foreign state investments amounted to 3,866 billion soums in terms of ownership. This indicator was 457.7 billion soums more than in 2014. At the beginning of 2015, the state share was 572.4 billion, and the share of non-governmental organizations was 3293.6 billion soums. Out of this (3293.6) 569.6 billion soums belonged to the private property of citizens, 1389.7 billion soums to the association of farms, 1212.6 billion to joint ventures, foreign citizens and organizations, and 121.7 billion soums to other similar small entrepreneurs.

Thus, during the 20-year history of independence (1992-2010), the volume of attracting foreign investments in our country has been steadily increasing. In particular, in the Bukhara region, foreign investments were attracted to the most important production facilities, and significant economic growth took place. However, the lack of experience in this direction and the cases of non-effective use of samoyas are also noticeable.

In January-December 2015, investments in the amount of 3878.4 billion soums were made to increase the main capital of the region, and the growth rate was 102.1 percent compared to the same period last year.

3,047.3 billion soums or 78.6% of the total amount of investments in fixed capital were directed to production sectors, 831.1 billion soums or 21.4% were directed to non-production sectors.

In conclusion, the introduction of foreign investments into the Bukhara region has led to significant changes in the life of the region's population. For example, the

establishment of joint ventures employed certain people of the population, and encouraged the representatives of the population who are passionate about entrepreneurship to establish their own businesses faster, increasing their desire to open new enterprises.

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